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Research Article

**VALIDATED UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR
ESTIMATION OF GEMCITABINE IN BULK AND DOSAGE
FORM****Dr. K. Padmalatha , Vijaya Durga. D, Sk. Salma, N. Naga Lakshmi, Ch. Janaki,
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Article Received: April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of the present work was to develop and validate a novel, specific, precise and reliable method for estimation of gemcitabine hydrochloride in bulk and polymeric nanoparticles using UV-visible spectroscopy method.

Methods: The UV-Visible spectrophotometric determination was performed with double beam Systronics UV-visible spectrophotometer; model UV-2201 (India). The proposed methods were validated for various parameters like linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness, detection, quantification limits, and formulation analysis as per international conference on harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

Results: The method was based on measurement of absorbance at wavelength maxima i.e. 260 nm, λ_{max} of the drug in distilled water. The method obeyed Beer Lambert's law in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and R²-value was found to be 0.999. Moreover, the % drug recovered from formulation was found to be 99.1%.

Conclusion: According to results, the currently developed method shows compliance with acceptance criteria with Q2 (R1) and international conference on harmonization (2005) guidelines, because the % RSD was found to be less than 2%. The developed method was simple, accurate and précised.

Keywords: Gemcitabine Hydrochloride, UV-Visible Spectrophotometer, Correlation coefficient, λ_{max}

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INTRODUCTION:

Analytical research and development is a requisite part of the pharmaceutical industry whose goals include contributing to the development of new active substances and pharmaceutical dosage forms by providing information based on analytical chemistry, by developing analytical methods and specifications used in quality control of materials for toxicological and clinical trails.

Gemcitabine acts by inhibition of DNA synthesis. It is deaminated by deoxycytidine deaminase to 2',2'-difluoro deoxy uridine (dFdU) or activated by deoxycytidine kinase to dFdC-5'-monophosphate(dFdCMP). Chemically Gemcitabine is 4-amino-1-(2-deoxy-2,2-difluoro-β-D-erythro-pentofuranosyl) pyrimidin-2(1H)-on. Gemcitabine is used in the treatment of various carcinomas. It is first line treatment alone for pancreatic cancer .it is given by injection into a vein.

Structure of

Gemcitabine

Gemcitabine has a molecular weight (263.2 g/mol) of molecular formula (C₉H₁₁F₂N₃O₄), its melting point (168.64°C), half-life for Short Infusions (32-94 mins) and long infusions (245-638 mins). It is slightly soluble in methanol, practically insoluble in ethanol and polar organic solvents, soluble in water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents:

Gemcitabine HCL is supplied as gift sample by Hetero Labs Ltd, Hyderabad, Telangana. Methanol and Acetonitrile from SD-Fine chemicals limited. All chemicals and reagents used in the study are of analytical grade.

Instrumentation:

A single beam T60U UV-Spectrophotometer, model UV-3000⁺(Lab India) with a spectral bandwidth of 2 nm was performed in 10 mm quartz cells. Weighing Balance of model Gold-300P(Phoenix) and Sonicator of model 2K13016(LIFE CARE).

Preparation of solvent system:

Gemcitabine was known to be soluble in solvents like water, methanol, acetonitrile. The absorption pattern of resulting solution is measured against respective blank solution in UV range (200 – 400 nm) and λ_{max} was found in each solvent. The λ_{max} found in each solvent was compared with UV cutoff of the particular solvent to avoid any interaction between the sample peak and solvent peak.

Preparation of standard stock solution and working solution:

The standard solution was prepared by accurately weighing 100 mg of Gemcitabine in 100 mL volumetric flask containing 30 mL of diluent and sonicated for about 30 min, and then the volume was made up to the mark with the same diluent to get the final concentration of 1000 µg/mL. From the above solution 10 mL was pipette out into a 100 mL volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with diluent to get final concentration of 100 µg/mL (working standard solution). Pipette out 1ml from working standard into a clean 10ml standard volumetric flask and filter through 0.45 µ membrane filter. Make up the final volume with diluent to get final concentration of 10 µg/ml.

Procedure for calibration curve:

The standard solution was prepared by accurately weighing 100 mg of Gemcitabine in 100 mL volumetric flask containing 30 mL of diluent and sonicated for about 30 min, and then the volume was made up to the mark with the same diluent to get the final concentration of 1000 µg/mL. From the above solution 10 mL was pipette out into a 100 mL volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with diluent to get final concentration of 100 µg/mL (working standard solution).

Assay of gemcitabine:

Accurately weighed 20.62 mg of powder was transferred to clean 100 ml standard volumetric flask. Add few ml of diluent and dissolve, make up the final volume with diluent. The solution is sonicated for 30 min and marked as sample stock solution. Pipette out 1ml from sample stock into a clean 10ml standard volumetric flask and filter through 0.45 µ membrane filter. Make up the final volume with diluent to get final concentration of 10 µg/ml.

Validation of methods:

Linearity: The aliquots of concentration ranging 5-30 µg/ml were analyzed. The results obtained were used to calculate the equation of the line by using linear regression by the least-squares regression method.

Accuracy: The accuracy of the method is the closeness of the measured value to the true value for the sample. For recovery study, the solutions were prepared at levels 50%, 100% and 150% of test solution and taken absorbance of each solution.

Precision: The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions. Precision was determined as system precision and method precision, in accordance with ICH guidelines. The results of system and method precision studies were shown in the following table. The low %RSD values obtained from the analysis of tablets indicated that the method was highly precise.

Robustness and ruggedness:

The robustness of the proposed method was tested by changing parameters such as wavelength, temperature and pH. Ruggedness was determined by different analysts, different laboratory, different instrument, different lots of chemical etc. and the results were reported in terms of % RSD.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ):

These limits, which are defined based on each experiment, are never “true values”, but can only

be approximate estimations. Indeed, the calculated values are biased- like all results obtained throughout experiments and will vary from one matrix to a different, from one instrument to another, from one day to another, and from one laboratory to another.

The limits are commonly associated with the signal to noise ratio (S/N). In the case of LOD, analysts often use S/N (signal to noise ratio) of 2:1 or 3:1, while a S/N of 10:1 is often considered to be necessary for the LOQ. Typically, the signal is measured from the base line to peak apex and divided by the peak-to-peak noise, which is determined from the blank plasma injection.

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma / S$$

$$LOD = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

Where, σ - Standard deviation from response
S - Slope from calibration curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of absorption maxima (λ max):

Appropriate volume 2.0 ml of standard stock solution of Gemcitabine was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to a mark with distilled water to give a concentration of 20 μ g/ml. The resulting solution was scanned in the UV range(200 – 400 nm). In spectrum Gemcitabine showed absorbance maximum at 260 nm.

Absorption spectrum of GEMCITABINE (260nm)

Linearity:

A series of solutions of standard drug substance were prepared in the concentration ranging from 5-30 μ g/mL Gemcitabine a calibration graph is plotted between amount of Concentration Vs Absorbance.

Correlation co-efficient (r^2) of the linearity study were found to be 0.999 with linear regression equations $y = 0.1091x - 0.1031$, for Gemcitabine, which proves that the method is linear over the Concentration range of drug.

Table 1: Linearity Data of Gemcitabine

S.No	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	5	0.126
3	10	0.228
4	15	0.324
5	20	0.441
6	25	0.546
7	30	0.667

Calibration Curve for Gemcitabine

Overline spectrum of Gemcitabine

Precision (System and Method precision):

Precision was determined as

System precision:

The system precision was established by injecting six replicate injections of standard solution into the chromatographic system by maintaining the optimized Spectroscopic conditions.

Method precision:

Six samples of drug product of $20 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of the working test concentration were prepared and injected into the Spectroscopic system.

Table 2: System and Method Precision Data of Gemcitabine

S.NO	Wave Length	Absorbance(System precision)	Absorbance(Method precision)
1	260	0.442	0.432
2	260	0.440	0.439
3	260	0.444	0.441
4	260	0.442	0.438
5	260	0.441	0.442
6	260	0.443	0.436
Mean	-	0.442	0.438
S.D	-	0.001291	0.0033
%RSD	-	0.29208	0.75

Accuracy:

The accuracy was carried out by adding known amounts of standard drug to the analyte (three concentrations levels - 50, 100 and 150 % - of the labeled claim). At each level, three determinations were performed and the results were recorded. The accuracy was expressed as percent analyte recovered by the proposed method

Table 3: Accuracy Data of Gemcitabine

S.No	Spiked level	Absorbance	% Recovery	S.D	%RSD	Mean Recovery
1	50%	0.326	101.0	0.7789	0.77	99.7
		0.328	102.0			
		0.324	99.17			
2	100%	0.445	99.2	0.0012	0.54	99.7
		0.442	100			
		0.440	100.9			
3	150%	0.548	101.5	1.7619	0.93	98.7
		0.542	99.66			
		0.544	100.33			

Robustness:

The following changes were made in the spectroscopic system to determine the effect of deliberate variations in the optimized spectroscopic conditions like wave length, Temperature etc.

Table 4: Robustness Data Change in wave length of Gemcitabine

S. No	Change in wave length	Absorbance	%RSD
1	Low (259nm)	0.438	0.738
2	Original(260nm)	0.442	
3	High (261nm)	0.446	

Table 5: Robustness Data Change in Temperature of Gemcitabine

S. No	Change in Temperature	Absorbance	%RSD
1	Low (20°C)	0.436	0.83
2	Original (25°C)	0.441	
3	High (30°C)	0.445	

Ruggedness:

The ruggedness of an analytical method was the degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same samples under a variety of test conditions like different analysts, different laboratory, different instrument, different lots of chemical etc. The sample solution of 15 µg / mL was prepared in triplicate and their relative absorbances were measured at variable conditions. The % RSD of the results analogous to the absorbances were conveyed.

Table 6: Ruggedness Data of Gemcitabine

	Different analysts		Different labs		Different Instruments	
	Ch. Janaki	U. Sony	Lab-1	Lab-2	PG Instrument T60	Lab India
Absorbance	0.324	0.323	0.326	0.321	0.319	0.321
	0.328	0.322	0.324	0.324	0.324	0.324
	0.325	0.320	0.322	0.321	0.322	0.323
%RSD	0.45%		0.46%		0.56%	

DETECTION LIMIT AND QUANTITATION LIMIT (LOD & LOQ):

The limits are commonly associated with the signal to noise ratio (S/N). In the case of LOD, analysts often use S/N (signal to noise ratio) of 2:1 or 3:1, while a S/N of 10:1 is often considered to be necessary for the LOQ.

$$\begin{aligned} LOQ &= 10 \sigma / S \\ &= 10 \times 0.000492 / 0.018 \\ &= 0.27 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} LOD &= 3.3 \sigma / S \\ &= 3.3 \times 0.000492 / 0.018 \\ &= 0.09 \mu\text{g/ml} \end{aligned}$$

Where, σ - Standard deviation from response S - Slope from calibration curve.

Table 7: Detection Limit and Quantitation Limit Data of Gemcitabine

Parameters	Gemcitabine
Detection Limit (LOD)	0.09
Limit and Quantitation (LOQ)	0.27

Table 8: Summary of all the validation parameters

Parameters	RESULTS	ACCEPTANCE LIMITS
	GEMCITABINE	
Specificity	—	No interference
Linearity	0.999	$r^2 = 0.999$
Accuracy	99.9	98-102%
Precision	RSD < 1%	RSD < 2%
Robustness	RSD < 2%	RSD < 2%
LOD	0.09	Signal noise ratio should be more than 3:1
LOQ	0.27	Signal noise ratio should be more than 10:1
Assay	99.1%	98-102%

CONCLUSION:

An UV Spectrophotometric method was developed and validated for various parameters as per ICH Guidelines. Distilled water was selected as diluent for proposed method for quantification of Gemcitabine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The Gemcitabine showed maximum absorbance at 260nm using water as diluent. For routine analytical purposes it is always of interest to establish methods capable of analysing a sample in a short time period with due accuracy and precision. The main purpose of the study was to develop specific, accurate, precise and economic methods for the determination of Gemcitabine.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS:

The authors declare that they do not have any financial and personal relationships with other

people or any other organizations that could inappropriately influence this research work.

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